

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

ANGELA MERKEL STATESMAN AND POLITICIAN

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Abstract

Today, Germany is the leading country in the European Union. Germany's success in the following decades was directly related to the work of Chancellor Angela Merkel, who led the government. This article Angela Merkel's come to government and political activities were analyzed

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Today, Germany is the leading country in the European Union. Germany's success in the following decades was directly related to the work of Chancellor Angela Merkel, who led it.

Germany has developed rapidly under the leadership of this woman for more than ten years. Germany has developed not only politically, but also socio-economically. For this reason, the study of Germany, which has achieved such achievements, and Angela Merkel's activities related to it, is relevant today.

Since the management history of Angela Merkel and her administration is directly connected with modern history, this issue is covered mainly in periodicals. However, special scientific research works on this have not been carried out until today. The subject has been studied by other authors of the world, mainly as a partial stop in the process of studying the history of Germany. That's why we aim to study it separately in this article.

Angela Dorothea Merkel was born on July 17, 1954 in the family of Horsta Kasner and Gerlinda Kasner in Hamburg. A few days after Angela's birth, her family moved from Hamburg to Perleberg, GDR. In 1957, Angela's family also came to this city due to the transfer of her priest father to the Temple City Church. Angela's mother was a teacher who taught Latin and English. Angela also had a brother Marcus and a sister Irena.

According to the memories of her former classmates and teachers, Angela (then surname Kasner) did not stand out in any way, except for her achievements in mastering the Russian language and mathematics. As a member of the pioneer organization at school, Angela wore a blue tie (in the former GDR, the pioneer organization members did not wear a red tie, as in the USSR), and the fact that Angela would eventually take the position of Chancellor of Germany, no one could have imagined.

In the eighth year of her chancellorship, Angela Merkel has reached the zenith of her power – again. She has now been at the head of the greatest and richest economy in Europe for two parliamentary terms. She is the undisputed leader of her party and faces almost no opposition. She presides over a cabinet of mostly loyal and obedient ministers. She has tamed her second coalition partner, putting to rest the initial negative impression of her government. She treats the opposition with

disdain. Publicly, she enjoys a great deal of respect – no chancellor before her had been able to call on such high approval ratings in their seventh year of government. Economically, her country is not in a bad shape – compared to its neighbours. Nor is Germany troubled by any major problems at home.

Angela Merkel has risen to a position of power and worldwide influence. She is one of a small group of heads of state who can look back on a similarly long period in office. In the European Union she is the last of her generation of leaders: apart from that perennial, the Prime Minister of Luxembourg, no one has been in power longer than she has. The President of the European Commission took office the year before her – but only with her help. Merkel is working with the second American President of her time in office, and she had dealings with their predecessor. She is engaged in a kind of hare-and-tortoise race with the President of Russia as to who will stay in office longest. In China Merkel has so far seen only one change of leadership: she eagerly anticipated her meeting with the new leaders, wishing to compare the new politicians in power with their familiar predecessors [1].

Merkel started her political career in 1990. Since the fall of the "Berlin Wall" in the fall of 1989, many things have changed in the life of Angela Merkel, along with millions of Germans. In particular, the emergence of new democratic parties, the termination of the Academy of Sciences of the former GDR, where he worked, encouraged him to join the "Democratic Uprising" movement. Angela, who is a physicist by profession, starts working in this party as an EHM administrator. Later, he also works as a referent, a member of the propaganda group. This party, which started as an opposition movement to the government, later joined the coalition with the Christian-Social Union and the Christian-Democrat parties. At that time, the leader of this block was Federal Chancellor Helmut Kohl, a prominent political figure of his time [2].

By the fall of 1989, with the fall of the Berlin Wall and the beginning of democratic processes in the GDR, along with the dissolution of the GDR FA, Angela joined the newly formed party "Democratic Breakthrough". Merkel's position in the party was lucky. From 1989 to 1990, he was a member of the "Democratic Eruption" party. Since 1990, he has been a deputy of the Christian Democratic Union (XDI), and in 1990-

1998 he was appointed to the position of deputy chairman of this party.

After the elections in the GDR, he became the official representative of the East German government. From this year, he takes the post of press secretary of the GDR government headed by Lothar de Maiziere, the first and only non-communist. Since December 1990, he has been a deputy in the Bundestag of the GFR [3].

From January 1991 to 1994, after the personal proposal of Gelmut Koll, he was appointed Minister of Women and Youth Affairs. By 1994, Angela Merkel held the position of Minister of Environment and Nature Protection, Nuclear Safety. Probably because he did not come up with any serious initiative, almost not many people remember his time as a minister. But from time to time he did not forget to show his loyalty to his mighty patron [2].

Angela Merkel included "humanity, fair treatment of all generations, love for nation and homeland, fight against bureaucracy" in the party's program of action. All this was still not enough to recommend his candidacy for the post of federal chancellor. That's when Mrs. Merkel makes good use of strategy and behind-the-scenes games. In addition, Mrs. Merkel managed to find an ally across the ocean: unlike the leaders of the ruling party, she openly supported the actions of the George Bush administration in Iraq.

When Angela Merkel was elected Chancellor of Germany on November 22, 2005, German women took it as their personal success. This event was remarkable in the history of Germany in two respects: firstly, a woman had never been in charge of the government in German history (except for Feophane, the empress who lived in the 10th century); secondly, until then, none of the representatives of the former socialist state - the GDR had risen to such a high position.

At first glance, she is not much different from ordinary housewives, a simple and sincere woman. But her ambitions, her ability to assess the situation correctly and her ability to work show who this woman really is. His inconspicuous appearance and alienation from suspicious behavior serve as a mask for him to confuse his opponents on the way to the chancellor's seat.

In the activity program announced in 2006, Angela Merkel indicated that she would carry out fundamental reforms in the areas of the federal system, budget and financial system, scientific research, energy policy, family, labor market and health care, as well as the fight against bureaucracy. Despite the fact that clear goals and tasks were not defined, its management method was initially supported by a wide segment of the population, representatives of the business world and foreign partners.

In a very short period of time, his popularity reached high ratings: in 2006 polls, 80 percent of the

German population expressed satisfaction with his policies. His government began to achieve positive results in the economy, particularly in reducing unemployment [2]

A period of peace reigned at the beginning of the new term of the Bundestag under Merkel and her cabinet. In late March 2006, Merkel presented her eight-point plan for the second half of her term. It shows the main directions of reforming the federal system, the fight against bureaucracy, scientific research, energy policy, budget and financial policy, family, labor market, and especially the health care system.

Despite the lack of visible decisive actions, the business-like way of managing the state will initially win the approval of the population and win business abroad. "Forbes" magazine named Angela Merkel the most famous woman in the world in 2006, 2007 and 2008, and "Times" magazine included the Chancellor of the Federal Republic of Germany in 2006 and 2007 among the hundred most famous people on the planet.

By 2013, it was predicted that the outlook for the German economy might not be positive for the coming months. The Bundesbank's November report downgraded business forecasts and noted no new industrial orders [4].

Environmental protection. In April 1995, Angela Merkel, as German Minister of Environment, hosted the first UN Nature Conference in Berlin. The Berlin Mandate was the first document to attract international efforts to reduce greenhouse gases. In subsequent negotiations, Angela Merkel approached the Kyoto Protocol in 1997 to set sufficiently high emission reduction targets. Angela Merkel is a supporter of the peaceful use of nuclear power and nuclear power plants to obtain electricity. In his position, he was also responsible for dealing with the use of nuclear waste. In May 1998, it became known about the increasing importance of radiation in "Castor" containers sent to France. The opposition demanded the resignation of Minister Merkel for violating her supervisory functions. However, Merkel shows that she is exercising her basic powers and that her federal lands and the nuclear industry are responsible [4].

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